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ABSTRACTS

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New Pertussis Vaccine for Intranasal Delivery

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Abstract: Pertussis is a respiratory disease that poses a severe threat to both newborns and elderly individuals. The transmission of the disease primarily occurs *via* human-to-human contact, predominantly via respiratory droplets that become aerosolized. Presently, there are two types of vaccines *viz.* whole cell and acellular pertussis, employed for the prevention of this ailment. But the recent resurgence of pertussis has highlighted the limitations of these vaccines and led to the conceptualization of new ideas to formulate a new pertussis vaccine capable of controlling asymptomatic carriage and blocking of human-to-human transmission. These include addition of new antigens, search of new mucosal adjuvants and delivery of pertussis vaccine through intranasal route. In the present investigation, antigens PRN, PT and FHA from acellular pertussis vaccine were encapsulated individually as well as co-encapsulated using PLGA, in conjunction with the mucosal adjuvant CpG ODN. These antigen formulations were then delivered intranasally to generate immune response at the portal of pathogen entry. In the study it is observed that although pertussis antigen PT, FHA and PRN were capable of generating IgG antibodies when delivered individually but a superior immune response was achieved when a formulation containing all three antigens PT, FHA and PRN was used for immunization. But this immune response was further improved by formulating PT, FHA and PRN in combination with each other and encapsulating using PLGA nanoparticles along with mucosal adjuvant CpG ODN.

Keywords: Pertussis vaccine, nasal delivery, nanoparticles, PLGA, CpG ODN.

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